

A STUDY OF REVIEWS TO UNDERSTAND THE REASONS OF MIGRATION IN NEIGHBOURING COUNTRIES OF INDIA

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Abstract:

Migration is a vital state for the existence for anthropoid and so it does exist in one or other form, overpowering all the barriers, natural or artificial. It is an important phenomenon which has touched almost all aspects of life - social, economic, political, cultural, health and hygiene. This may be the probable reason we find several studies have been made and enormous literatures exist. This is a review paper on migration of earlier studies and literatures related with the topic, so as to provide it with a firm basis. The reviews are at International and National level. This paper is an attempt to study and understand the various reasons of migration at International level.

Key Words: Migration, International, Youth, Reviews & Reasons

Introduction:

The patterns of migration have always rivetted the demographers. Migration is becoming a very common term and the youngsters today are very much wanting to move away from the land in which they are born.

Objective of the Study:

The main objective of the study is to study the different reasons of migration in neighboring countries of India

Research Methodology:

The researcher reviewed several literatures to identify the reasons of migrations in the neighboring countries and has mentioned the conclusions in each case.

The reviews studied are arranged and the conclusion deduced in each work is mentioned.

- Cultural adaptation by Young people and their parents of Asian immigrants of Britain disclose that cultural integration existed among the first-generation immigrants; cultural assimilation in the case of second-generation immigrants and their children but complete neglect of their tradition and culture in the case of third generation immigrants and the younger people. [Kannan, C.T. (1978)]
Conclusion: Migration leads to cultural assimilation.
- Shekhar Mukherjee through his brief analysis presented the historical forces and constraints, which have created underdevelopment, spatial disarticulation and spatial organisation in South and South-East Asia. In order to reduce inequality, migration and its negative effects, he recommended for integration of demographic, social and economic planning within the framework of the regional planning [Shekhar Mukherjee (1981)]
Conclusion: Migration is the result of economic inequality and creates negative effect upon the origin through labour drain.
- A study based on U.S. Annual Housing Survey 1973-78 has revealed that migration in search of job has declined and at the same time migration due to job related transfers has increased which also explains that there exists a reduction in the market direct mobility. [Ralph R. Sell's (1983)]
Conclusion: Migration exist among all income, education and age groups
- A study on effects of external as well as internal remittances on income distribution, asset accumulation and inequality in rural areas of Pakistan found that internal remittances were mainly received by lower income groups and were mainly used for day-to-day requirements. [Adams, R.H. (1992)]
Conclusion: The effect of internal remittance on overall income inequality was very much limited whereas external remittances were mainly received by upper income groups and it played an important role in income inequality.
- The role of women in migration, the importance of family ties, the contextual causes of migration and the characteristics of migration flows based on narratives are explained through the story of "Amma". [Beret Helene Vandemb (199~)]

Conclusion: Narratives based on stories of individuals explain individual behaviour in relation to the structural forces and has an important place in the study of Third World Migration.

- A study dealt with mass migration from the developing countries to the developed countries due to environmental catastrophes; the hostile attitude of receiving countries and the resultant conflicts in the developing countries. [Ashok Swain's (1996)]

Conclusion: The major reason for such mass migration is the environmental exploiters in the developing countries which has become a threat to the peace and security of many developing nations. Efforts should be taken to control environmental deconstruction, giving adherence to sustainable development, which can reduce migration and for that purpose development planning should be undertaken after incorporating migration, external assistance and population planning.

- Study on the causal relationship between migration and employment changes, causes and consequences of migration revealed that both employment and migration affect each other. The effect of employment on net migration is stronger than that of the vice versa [Jisuk Chun (1996,7)]

Conclusion: Economic factors like employment and investment opportunities are the most important determinants of migration and migration is a means of achieving economic efficiency and equality.

- An analysis on major migration streams, migration rates, and net migration for blacks and whites in U.S, to study the primary, return and onward interstate migration pattern for each category [Bruce New Bold, K. (1997)]

Conclusion: Migration pattern of blacks resembles to that of the whites, but return migration was higher among blacks, and their onward migration rates were also lower.

- International migration in the contest of liberalisation [Prabhat Patnaik and Chandra Sekhar's (1998)]

Conclusion: there is a labour scarcity, advanced countries allow immigrants from backward countries; while in times of recessions they turn against migrants propagating that immigrants steal jobs, creating a feeling of frustration among the immigrants. The argument was liberalisation denies migrants even the solace of imagining that there is a "home country" where their role, contribution, or money they send are being appreciated and where they would be welcomed back as valued citizens.

- Separation from family and social, cultural norms; isolation/loneliness, more sexual freedom, and inadequate financial resources make migrants more vulnerable to adopting high risk sexual behaviour, along with the living and working conditions of poverty, powerlessness and social instability make them more vulnerable to HIV/AIDS [UNAIDS and IOM's (1998)]

Conclusion: There are chances of infection on migration, transit, and on return; illegal and undocumented migrants have the least access to health and other medical facilities.

- Migrants in rural and urban areas of Kenya are more likely to practice unsafe sex or high-risk sex [Brockhoof and Biddlecom (1999,11)]

Conclusion: migration can contribute to increase in the incidence and spread of HIV/AIDS has led to imposition of some travel restriction on the infected.

- Studies on determinants and impact of remittances on migrant sending areas. It was found that inflows of remittances in to the sending economies are large but its influence is overlooked. Further, the economic environments that encourage out-migration also limit the potentials for migrant remittances to stimulate development in sending areas. [Edward Taylor, J. (1999)12]

Conclusion: Migration is not a panacea or a substitute for good economic policies.

- Studies dealing with the illegal emigration and emigrants of Chinese in to the United States observed that, even though globalisation has led to free movement of goods, but it has not lifted the constraints on the mobility of labour, especially from less developed countries, and this has led to a new type of business - smuggling of migrants. [Chin, K.L (1999)13]

- Conclusion: The study recommended to the Chinese Government to allow freedom to its citizens to travel abroad

- Study of job preferences of Pakistani international return migrants, found that those having higher savings opted for self-employment and others opted wage-employment, and age or retirement from local labour market does not appear to influence their choices. [Nadeem Ilahi (1999)14]

Conclusion: International migration and return help in the development of small businesses with the capital mobilised through the accumulation of over-seas savings.

- On studying the process of arranging sponsorship works and getting visas in Kuwait. [Nasra M Shah and Indu Menon (1999)15]

Conclusion: Social network of friends and relatives has an important role in this migration process

- The data collected from internal migrants in Turkey on linkage between migration and earnings so as to examine the implication of rationality in migration revealed that both migrants and non- migrants chose the option in which they had relative benefit. It was observed that the estimated gain from migration is negative for a major part of migrants and minority realised very high returns [Insan Tunali (2000)17]

Conclusion: migration decisions are a risky undertaking or a lottery.

- Researches on child migration explained the magnitude and geography of internal and international child migration in Britain in 1990s [Janet Dobson and John Still Well (2000)]

Conclusion: Problems of child migrants by researchers was neglected and requested to focus more attention and research on the relationship between child migration and school systems

- A study of inter-provincial migration of Spain found an increasing trend in short distance migration and a declining trend in long distance migration. It was also found that majority of migrants were in the working age group and the peak migration probability was persons aged 26 [John Stillwell et. a1 (2000)"]

Conclusion: Internal migration has helped to reshape the nation's population distribution.

- Using the migration determinants and analysing the previous experiences of member countries of European Union, researchers tried to forecast the migration pattern that may result from the forthcoming eastward enlargement and the effect on the labour market of the Union [Elmar Honekopp and Hienz Werner (2000)]

Conclusion: The major reason for migration is the economic imbalance and since the disparity between member countries is negligible, the fear of large-scale migration is wrong. But inequality that exists between some of the member-countries may encourage migration.

- Studies on importance and role of specific configuration network ties in migration flows and occupational pattern based on life histories of Gujarati Indian migrants in New York and London [Maritsa V Poros (2001)]

Conclusion: Network ties like organisational and community relationships, interpersonal ties like friendship etc have an important role in migration and availability of employment at the destination.

- Comparisons on internal migrations in Australia and Britain in the early 1980s and 1990s found that that the Australians have higher propensity to migrate; migration distance in Australia is longer than that of Britain and frictional effect of distance on migration is lower [Bell. M, Blake et. a1 (2002)]

Conclusion: Migration effectiveness is higher in Britain than in Australia and migration in Australia generates greater re-distribution of population because of higher intensity. [Carlos R Azzoni et. a1 (2002)]

- Wage inequality in different regions of Brazil was analysed and found that cost of living index, education, region, experience as well as race contributed for wage differences [Carlos R Azzoni et. a1 (2002)]

Conclusion: Cost of living index, education, region, experience as well as race contributed for wage differences

- Studies on the relationship between migration and economic development in Sri Lanka as well as the socio- economic context in which migration and development took place [Dhananjayan Sriskanda Rajah (2002)]

Conclusion: Remittances from migrants to the Sri Lankan economy is an important part of foreign exchange earnings and it has played and will play an important role in household development and local economies in labour sending regions.

- Most of the migrations are undertaken for a more secured livelihood and have led to reduction in poverty and inequality as well as for educational improvement of children of migrants. Clare Waddington (2003)

Conclusion: Remittance is a major source of income to the migrant households for their daily requirements as well as for accumulation. But, sometimes migration, which is due to vulnerability, may further increase vulnerability.

- Studied the size and features of migration within and out of Africa. Timothy J. Haton and Jeffrey G. Williamson (2003)

Conclusion: In sub-Saharan Africa, the difference in wages and population pressure were the major reasons for out migration to Europe in nineteenth centuries.

Conclusions of the Researcher:

The researcher always wondered why is that there exist so much enthusiasm among the brilliant brains to move out of their own country which helped them to grow, rather than working for it. After studying and understanding the above reviews, the researcher could conclude that the major reasons of migration is the difference in the source and size of income /wages which attracts migrants from one country to the other

Future Scope of Research:

Understanding the reasons of migration was a priority for the researcher, so that this information on migration can further help in future researches on reasons for migration of youth from our country.

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